

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KARADAVUT****FIRST NAME: GOEKHAN****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes).
The author did use Zotero to insert references.
The author did use Grammarly Premium.
The author used the following software: (e.g., MS Word Office 365 on IOS).

QUIZ: ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE

- 1. Select the correct parenthetical citation (Turabian style) of the following quote: “Mike, come over here so we can start.”**
 - She was calling “come over here,” to start.¹
 - She was calling: “Come over here”, to start.
 - She was calling “(...) come over here (...)” to start.
 - She was calling “come over here”, to start.

- 2. According to Turabian (2013), the ideal structure of a qualitative research is:**
 - Abstract-Literature Review-Summary-Conclusion-Bibliography.
 - Introduction-Abstract-Abbreviation-Summary-Literature review.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 179.

- Introduction-Methods and Materials-Results-Discussion-Conclusion.²**
- Introduction-Research Problem-Methods-Literature Review-Conclusion.
3. **Select the sentence, which refers correctly to the following book title: *The Hours of International Fear***
- I am referring to the Hours of International Fear.
- I am referring to *The Hours of International Fear*.³**
- I am referring to: “the Hours of International Fear”.
- I am referring to “the Hours of International Fear.”
4. **According to Bloomberg and Volpe (2008), the introduction chapter contains:**
- Abstract, author’s bias, background knowledge.
- Background information, abbreviation, vocabularies.
- Purpose statement, descriptors, findings.
- Research problem, purpose statement, research questions.⁴**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 43.

³ Ibid., 185.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 167.

5. **A qualitative research purpose:**

- Seeks variation in findings.
- Seeks consensus (the norm).⁵**
- Combines quantitative and qualitative methods.
- Provides criticism to previous researches.

6. **The most subjective chapter in a qualitative research is:**

- Chapter 6-Conclusion and Recommendations.
- Chapter 1-Introduction.
- Chapter 3-Research Methodology.
- Chapter 5-Analysis and Interpretation of Findings.⁶**

7. **Which is the shortest chapter in a qualitative research?**

- Abstract.
- Introduction.⁷**
- Findings.
- Conclusion.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 185.

⁶ Ibid., 167.

⁷ Ibid., 36.

8. **The three question category types are according to Maxwell (2005):**

- Inductive, integrated, deductive.
- Descriptive, critical, logical.
- Descriptive, interpretive, theoretical.**⁸
- Inductive, interactive, argumentative.

9. **A literature review's content should (rule of thumb) refer to information not older than:**

- 5 years.**⁹
- 10 years.
- 1 century.
- 3 years.

10. **Knowledge is categorized into four philosophical categories:**

- Causality, axiology, logically, factual.
- Descriptive, explanatory, fundamental, fact-based.
- Natural, *justa causa, sine qua non*, axiology.
- Ontology, epistemology, axiology, methodology.**¹⁰

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 37.

⁹ Ibid., 49.

¹⁰ Ibid., 8.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

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